

8T – Gravity as a Non-Continuous Interaction

"I don't understand the world very well, but that's what I think." Richard Feynman.

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series in net variation representation and spin representation it is possible to demonstrate that the gravitational interaction is not continuous in time and in certain time intervals, it ceased to exist. The features of the gravitational interaction are correlated to the fact it is a prime composite that is time variant.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

As we currently regard gravity as a composite element, as time goes by, the primordial is generating larger and larger net variations, which could change the ratio of the gravitational "constant" of a star given by equations (2.2) and (2.3):

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.3)$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3}$$

$$[N_{VK1}, N_{VK2}, N_{VK3}] \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$K1 \dots KN \in \mathbb{R}$$

However, the net variation N_{VK3} suddenly vanish from the combination and being replaced by a distinct net curvature element that is larger and in agreement with the arrow of time. Now the gravitational constant of the star is stronger while the forces extending outward are the same.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4}$$

$$N_{VK3} \neq N_{VK4}$$

The structure of the gravity is invariant to the change of the element. Since the total spin is invariant, i.e. two, there is not a change in the nature of gravity; the structure is the same while the composite element could be different.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose that at a certain time interval at a given fermion cluster known as a star, the gravitational force is described and measured by the term:

$$t_1 = [(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

At a later continuation in time on the same star gravity is measured as:

$$t_1 + \Delta t = [(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

In between the time interval the gravitational magnitude has varied, we already discussed it in detail in the 8T thesis. The point which was not analyzed is that during that element switching in time, there was a period in which gravity has ceased to exist. That is if we assume that the new element did not get immediately after the "original" has left. In that time the gravitational term had only two terms of net variation that we cannot associate to gravity as in spin representation it does not align on spin two. In contrast to interactions that are independent, interactions which are prime composite cannot be regarded as constants nor as continuous in time. There could be several interactions of gravity which will result in a certain average. Since this interaction is so weak due to the large total variations, measuring those variations most likely would be beyond our technological reach. The key point to take that in between the switching of the elements, gravity has ceased to exist and was re-ignited as the new element was inserted onto the coupling term. It is implicitly assumed that those extra terms are not generated by the majestic three as the first element but rather due to different generator of the same kind. As one stated before, Gravity due the number of elements varying and due to it's higher spin is still subject to analysis even with the recent developments of the primordial coupling series and the main equation of the 8T. The fact that we can state the equivalence principle as in equation (1) does not mean we understand well the gravitational interaction at quantum scales. As the inimitable Feynman once made a remark, which one finds appropriate in this context: "I know what it means to know something".

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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